

Organizational Socialization Levels in Nurses

M. Aslan, A. Karaaslan, S. Selcuk

Abstract—The research was conducted in order to determine the organizational socialization levels of nurses working in hospitals in the form of a descriptive study.

The research population was composed of nurses employed in public and private sector hospitals in the province of Konya with 0-3 years of professional experience in the hospitals (N=1200); and the sample was composed of 495 nurses that accepted to take part in the study voluntarily. Statistical evaluation of data was conducted in SPSS.16 software.

The results of the study revealed that the total score taken by nurses at the organizational socialization scale was 262.95; and this was close to the maximum score. Particularly the departmental socialization sub-dimension proved to be higher in comparison to the other two dimensions (organization socialization and task socialization). Statistically meaningful differences were found in the levels of organization socialization in relation to the status of organizational orientation training, level of education and age group.

Keywords— Nurses, Newcomers, Organizational Socialization

I. INTRODUCTION

ORGANIZATIONAL Socialization is a process aimed at the fulfillment of the standards and norms following the selection and evaluation of employees in which individuals learn [20], adopt and display the appropriate behavior for the organization [18], teach employees the knowledge that is important in the organization and the work environment [10], and this process encompasses both the employee and the organization at the same time [2]-[9].

An organization uses the socialization process for the adaptation of new members, and this process has a significant impact on both new members and the organization [17]. The means used by organizations in order to socialize new employees are crucial, because it would have an impact on the adaptation and socialization success of new employees [16]. If the socialization process proves to be successful, new workers will have a high performance and work satisfaction [6]. In the socialization process, workers not only learn the history, policy, language, targets, values and rules of an organization; but they also receive information on the group they belong and the task they fulfill in order to be successful [21].

Individual responses to the socialization initiative are divided into three categories [2]:

- **Revolt-Rebellion:** The individual adopts a hostile attitude against the socialization initiative of the organization, and

M. Aslan is with the Necmettin Erbakan University, Health Science Faculty, 42060, Konya, Turkey (corresponding author to provide phone: 09003323204049; fax: 09003323204059; e-mail: manaraslan@hotmail.com).

A. Karaaslan is with Necmettin Erbakan University, Health Science Faculty, 42060, Konya, Turkey (e-mail: karaaslanayfer58@gmail.com).

S. Selcuk is with Necmettin Erbakan University, Meram Medical Faculty Hospital, Nursing Services Manager, Konya, Turkey (e-mail: sselcuk@yahoo.com).

denies it. As a result, the individual may be fired, or sometimes can cause real change in the organization.

- **Creative Individualism:** The individual adopts the basic values and norms of the organization; but denies second level values and norms, and develops new ones instead.
- **Conformity:** Many individuals adapt to the organizational life by giving up on individualism and accepting all norms.

Organizational socialization is adaptation in a sense. Because adaptation is the individual's process of learning the attitudes and behaviors of the group they belong or will belong to. However, adaptation does not mean that the individual will not deviate from the group or organization behavior. Otherwise; full adaptation is not a kind of proper socialization; it makes it difficult for the individual to adjust to changing conditions. It is desirable for the newcomers of the organization to be creative. However, full adaptation and full rebellion kills creativity [14].

The fundamental purpose of socialization is to turn the employee into an effective member of the organization [3]. It is concerned with the compliance of employees in a given organization with the same norms and values and controlling and maintaining the process in these is shared throughout the organization. Employees can learn and apply the desired behavior through the socialization process [5]. Organizational socialization, which envisages that the newcomer becomes one of the insiders of the organization, is important because nurturing the newcomers requires high expenditures; and it would be costly if a high number of employees resign due to the failure of this process [2].

Organizational socialization is an approach applied in order to have the new members of the organization to maintain the existing culture. This process can either be conducted in a planned manner by the organization, or transpires randomly with the new employees observing and imitating the behaviors of other employees. The socialization process conducted by the organization is composed of orientation programs, training and development programs and success reviews. Adaptation programs ensure that employees learn the basic rules and processes within an organization and the identity of the organization. Training and development programs ensure that employees acquire the special work skills; and the values and attitudes associated with the organization [19].

States that raise employees is of central importance for their socialization by equipping them with information on the organization, their tasks and roles. Therefore, nurturing newcomers in the first couple of months of socialization can be influential on the newcomers' attitude towards the organization, and contribute to their adaptation [16].

Socialization process shows that newcomers concentrate on collecting information, acquire skills for the future, and try

to clarify their roles within the organization in the first couple of months of assignment [15].

At the end of the socialization process, the new employee will have acquired information on certain subjects [4]-[15]:

- Structure, purposes, history, traditions habits, language and policies of the organization;
- Groups and work units, important personalities, relations, attitudes and behaviors, way of communicating with colleagues, superiors and subordinates;
- Conduct of duties and tasks, required knowledge and skills, priorities, use of resources;
- Personal evolution that paves the way of identity, personal image and motivation.

II. METHOD

A. Type of Research

This is a descriptive study aimed at determining the organizational socialization levels of nurses.

B. Place of Research

6 public and 9 private sector hospitals were included in the scope of the research. Applications were performed in 5 public and 5 private sector hospitals based on permits.

C. Research Population and Sample

The research population was composed of 1200 nurses working in public and private sector hospitals in the province of Konya with 0-3 years of professional experience. The research sample was composed of a total of 495 nurses that accepted to fill in the questionnaires among these nurses.

D. Data Collection Technique and Instruments

Data were obtained by measuring dependent and independent variables. A questionnaire including six questions for the socio-demographic characteristics; the Organizational Socialization Scale which was developed by [21] and whose validity-reliability in Turkish was analyzed by [22] was used. Seven-point Likert scale responses were collected via 1- Strongly disagree 2- Disagree 3- Somewhat disagree 4- Neither agree nor disagree 5- Somewhat agree 6- Agree 7- Strongly agree. High scores mean the organizational socialization of the individual is at a proper level.

E. Research Variables

The independent variable of the study was demographic characteristics (Age, Gender, Level of Education, Years of Professional Experience, Years of Employment in The Organization, Orientation Training Status). The questionnaire developed by the researcher was used in order to determine the demographic characteristics.

The dependent variable was determined as the level of socialization.

F. Ethical Dimension of the Research

Written and verbal permissions were taken from the General Secretariat of Public Hospitals Union of Konya Province before the research was initiated. Moreover, verbal

permissions were also taken from the participants of the research.

G. Research Questions

- What are the organizational socialization levels of nurses working in hospitals?
- Is there a relation between the demographic characteristics and the organizational socialization levels?

H. Statistical Evaluation the Data

Data obtained from the research were uploaded to the electronic environment and analyzed by means of SPSS. 16 package software. The data were evaluated within 95% confidence interval, and significance was evaluated at $p < 0.05$ level.

Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, minimum and maximum scores were provided. In the statistical analysis of the data; independent sample t test was used in the comparison of averages between two groups in numerical variables; whereas unidirectional variance analysis was used in the comparison of categorical variables.

Values higher than $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

III. FINDINGS

The Organizational Socialization Scale which was developed by [21] and whose validity-reliability in Turkish was analyzed by [22] was used ($\alpha = 0.92$). When the Cronbach's alpha reliability value was calculated for the data reliability, it was found to be $\alpha = 0.96$ for the Organizational Socialization scale. The Cronbach's alpha value for the sub-dimensions of the scale was 0.90 for departmental socialization, 0.89 for task socialization and 0.93 for organization socialization.

Probing the distribution of total scores in the organizational socialization scale given in Table I; the lowest score received by nurses in the organizational socialization scale was found to be 47, and the highest score received was 329, with an average of 262.95 ± 44.570 . Delving into the distribution of scores in the sub-dimension of the scale; the lowest score taken in the organization socialization was 16, and the highest score was 112, with an average of 85.46 ± 17.521 . The lowest score in departmental socialization was 16, and the highest score was 133, with an average of 91.21 ± 15.626 . The lowest score in task socialization was 15, and the highest score was 105, with an average of 86.38 ± 13.533 .

TABLE I
 ORGANIZATIONAL SOCIALIZATION SCALE AND THE DISTRIBUTION OF SUB-DIMENSIONS (N: 495)

Scale and Sub-dimensions	Av.±sd	Min	Max
Organization Socialization	85.46±17.521	16	112
Departmental Socialization	91.21±15.626	16	133
Task Socialization	86.38±13.533	15	105
Total Score	262.95±44.570	47	329

Examining the organizational socialization scale socio-demographics of the nurses taking part in the study in given in

Table II, 79.5% of the participants were female, 89.5% received organizational orientation training, 67.3% had been employed by the organization for 13-36 months, 48.5% had an employment period of 36 months and longer, 44.2% were graduates of vocational healthcare schools, and 38% were aged 24-29. The average age of v the individuals participating in the study was 26.98 (SD: 6.23).

TABLE II
THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS AND EMPLOYMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE NURSES (N: 495)

Characteristics	N	%
Gender		
Female	369	74.5
Male	126	25.5
Organizational Orientation Training Status		
Yes	443	89.5
No	52	10.5
Years of Employment in the Organization		
0-6 months	44	8.9
6-12 months	118	23.8
13-36 months	333	67.3
Years of Professional Experience		
0-12 months	63	10.7
13-36 months	192	38.8
>36 months	240	48.5
Level of Education		
Vocational Healthcare School	219	44.2
Associate Degree	42	8.5
Bachelor of Science	198	40.0
Master's Degree	36	7.3
Age		
18-23 years old	152	30.7
24-29 years old	188	38.0
30-35 years old	101	20.4
36-41	42	8.5

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF THE AVERAGE TOTAL AND SUB-DIMENSION SCORES OF THE NURSES IN THE ORGANIZATIONAL SOCIALIZATION SCALE AND THEIR SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS (N: 495)

Characteristics	N	O.S.S X±SD	O. S X±SD	D.S X±SD	T. S X±SD
Gender					
F	369	263.8± 2.21	86.1± 16.69	91.4±15.00	86.4±12.87
M	126	260.2± 4.48	83.5± 19.68	90.4±17.36	86.2±15.35
t		0.78	1.29	0.61	0.16
p		0.43	0.19	0.53	0.86
Training Status					
Yes	443	266.9± 1.95	87.0± 16.30	92.5±14.49	87.5±12.38
No	52	229.0± 7.90	72.3±21.736	79.9±19.96	76.7±18.42
t		4.65	4.72	4.41	4.08
p		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

O.S.S: Organizational Socialization Scale
O.S: Organization Socialization
D.S: Departmental Socialization
T.S: Task Socialization

Table III shows the comparison of the average total and sub-dimension scores of the nurses in the organizational socialization scale and their socio-demographic characteristics. Accordingly; no statistically significant

difference was found between the average total scores and the average scores in the three sub-dimensions of the organizational socialization scale depending on the gender of the nurses ($p>.05$). The score received by male employees in the organizational socialization scale was 260.25; whereas the score received by female employees were 263.87.

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF THE AVERAGE TOTAL AND SUB-DIMENSION SCORES OF THE NURSES IN THE ORGANIZATIONAL SOCIALIZATION SCALE AND THEIR SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS (N: 495)

	N	O.S.S X±SD	O. S X±SD	D. S X±SD	T. S X±SD
LoE					
VHS ^a	219	268.5±2.94	87.3±17.64	93.9±14.87	88.1± 13.12
A.D ^b	42	257.2±6.80	82.9±18.42	88.8±15.65	85.3± 13.00
B.A ^c	198	257.2±3.28	83.6±17.24	89.1±16.51	84.4± 14.30
M.D ^d	36	266.7±6.49	86.8±16.45	92.2±13.60	87.6± 10.90
S.D		a>c (0.04)			a>c (0.03)
F		2.593	1.936	2.944	2.711
p		0.05	0.12	0.03	0.04
Age					
18-23 years old ^a	152	267.6±3.73	87.3±18.14	92.9±16.17	87.6±13.98
24-29 years old ^b	188	256.5±3.52	82.6±18.48	88.9±16.99	84.8±14.89
30-35 years old	101	266.6±3.42	86.6±14.74	92.5±11.75	87.3±10.13
34-41 years old ^d	42	258.79±6.390	85.31±15.39	89.19±15.05	84.29±12.65
≥42 years old	12	287.0±10.70	94.8±17.53	99.0±11.59	93.0±10.13
A.F				b>a.e (0.019)	b>a.e (0.013)
F		2.567	2.660	2.595	2.055
p		0.03	0.03	0.03	0.08

LoE: Level of Education
VHS: Vocational Healthcare School
A.D: Associate Degree
B.A: Bachelor of Arts
M.D: Master's Degree
S.D: Significant Difference

A statistically significant difference was found between the average total scores and the average scores in the three sub-dimensions of the organizational socialization scale depending on whether the nurses received organizational orientation training or not ($p<.05$).

The Comparison of the Average Total and Sub-dimension Scores of the Nurses in the Organizational Socialization Scale and their Socio-demographic characteristics were given in Table IV. Accordingly; a statistically significant difference was detected among the average scores of the nurses in the total score; department, and task-socialization sub-dimension scores of the nurses depending on the level of education ($p<.05$). In the Tukey progressive analysis conducted in order to determine between which education levels lies the difference, a significant difference was found between the nurses that graduated from vocational healthcare schools and the nurses that have a Bachelor of Arts degree ($p=0.046<0.05$).

A statistically significant difference was detected among the average scores of the nurses in the total score; organization, and department sub-dimension scores of the nurses depending on the age groups ($p<.05$). The LSD analysis conducted in order to determine among which age groups lays the

difference, a significant difference was found just in 24-29 age groups from the employees in the rest of the age groups.

No statistically significant difference was detected between the average total scores and the average scores in the three sub-dimensions of the organizational socialization scale depending on the years of professional experience of the nurses ($p > .05$).

No statistically significant difference was detected between the average total scores and the average scores in the three sub-dimensions of the organizational socialization scale depending on the years of employment in the organization of the nurses ($p > .05$).

IV. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to demonstrate the organizational socialization levels of nurses. Probing the sub-dimensions of the organizational socialization scale; the task dimension is related to the "assignment skills and how the task should be performed"; the department dimension dwells on "knowing how to interact with colleagues;" and the organization dimension indicates the "policies of the organization and its system of authority, culture and values" [15].

The total score received by the participating nurses in the organizational socialization scale was found to be 262.95; and is close to the maximum score. Departmental socialization sub-dimension score, in particular, was higher compared to the other two dimensions (91.21).

The organizational socialization scale scores of the nurses by gender revealed no statistically significant differences. These results comply with [11], who investigated the job satisfaction, motivation, acceptance, and loyalty dimensions; and found no significant relations by gender factor. The results of this study are also parallel to the results of the study conducted by [8].

The scores received by the nurses in the organizational socialization scale by age revealed that organizational socialization varies by age. The organizational socialization scale sub-dimensions demonstrate a difference in the organization and departmental socialization. 24-29 age group was found to be different than other age groups. Reference [1] found that there were no statistically significant differences in organizational socialization depending on age.

The organizational socialization scale scores of the nurses depending on the years of professional experience demonstrated that organizational socialization did not vary according to the years of professional experience. Whereas the studies conducted by [1]-[11] revealed a significant difference between the years of professional experience and organizational socialization.

The organizational socialization scale scores of the nurses depending on the years of employment in the organization revealed no differences in organizational socialization depending on the years of employment in the organization. In the related literature, [4] stated that the longer a person was employed by the organization, the better their socialization is, compared to the persons that were employed by the

organization for a shorter period. Moreover, a low level of relation was detected in the positive direction between the years of employment in the organization and the organizational socialization perceptions of teachers in a study named "A Procedural Analysis on the Organizational Socialization of Primary School Teachers." The longer the teachers worked in the organization, the higher their knowledge on the traditions and culture of the organizations and on their colleagues would be [13].

Socialization training programs are conducted in order to familiarize new employees with their job, colleagues, and the position of their duty within the organization. New employees learn about the goals of the organization at this training. Since socialization training was an activity related to the adaptation of new employees to the organization and work environment, it is a tactic used for the socialization of employees in a sense [7]. The organizational socialization scale scores of the nurses vary according to them received organizational orientation training or not. Departmental socialization displays higher scores compared to the other sub-dimensions.

The organizational socialization scale scores of the nurses depending on their level of education showed that organizational socialization varied according to the level of education; and there were differences in the departmental and task socialization sub-dimensions. It was revealed that nurses that were graduates of vocational healthcare schools had higher levels of organizational socialization compared to BA graduates. In the study named "The Organizational Socialization Levels of the Employees of the General Directorate of Youth and Sports," a relation was detected in the loyalty, acceptance, motivation, job satisfaction sub-dimension of organizational socialization depending on the education factor [12]. The LSD test aimed at finding the source of the difference revealed a significant separation between the high-school graduate employees and the rest of the employees.

V. RESULTS

The following results were obtained in light of the findings revealed by this study:

- Around three fourths of the nurses participating in the study were female; 38% were aged 24-29; and 44.2% were graduates of vocational healthcare schools;
- 48.5% of the nurses had a professional experience of over 3 years, 67.3% had been working in the organization for 1-3 years, and 89.5% received organizational orientation training,
- The average of the total scores the nurses received in the organizational socialization scale was 262.95 ± 44.570 ; and this score revealed that the organizational socialization scores of the nurses were close to the maximum score;
- There was not a relation between the gender, years of professional experience, years of employment in the organization and organizational socialization.
- There was a relation between the organizational orientation training status, age and level of education and organizational socialization.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Argon, "İlköğretim Okulu Öğretmenlerinin Örgütsel Sosyalleşme Düzeylerinin Çeşitli Değişkenler Açısından Değerlendirilmesi", e-Journal of New World Sciences Academy Education Sciences, 6(1), 197-207, Ocak 2011.
- [2] A. Balci, Örgütsel Sosyalleşme Kuram, Strateji ve Taktikler, Ankara, PEGEM A Yayıncılık, 2003.
- [3] H. Can, Organizasyon ve Yönetim, 4. Baskı, Ankara: Siyasal Kitabevi, 1997.
- [4] GT. Chao, A.M. O'Leary-Kelly, S. Wolf, HJ. Klein, and PD. Gardner, "Organizational Socialization: Its Content and Consequences", Journal of Applied Psychology, 79(5), 730-743, 1994.
- [5] H. Irene, S. Chow, "Organizational socialization and career success of Asian managers", International Journal of Human Resource Management, 13(4), 720-737, Şubat 2002.
- [6] T. Çalık, "İşgörenlerin Örgüte Uyumu", Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi, 2(1), 163-178, 2003.
- [7] T. Demirbilek, "Örgütsel sosyalleşmede işe alıştırma eğitiminin yeri ve önemi", S.Ü. İİBF Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi, 12(18), 353-373, 2009.
- [8] Z. Ghazali, "The influence of socialization agents and demographic profiles on brand consciousness", International Journal of Management and Marketing Research, 4(1), 19-29, 2011.
- [9] A.E.C Griffin, C. Adrienne, G. Srikanth, "Newcomer and organizational socialization tactics: an interactionist perspective", Human Resource Management Review, 10(4), 453-474.
- [10] C. Hamner, D. Organ, "Organizational Behavior an Applied Psychological Approach", Dallas, Texas: Business Pub, Inc, 1978.
- [11] S. Kartal, "İlköğretim okulu yönetici ve öğretmenlerinin örgütsel sosyalleşme düzeyleri," (Ankara ili örneği). Yayımlanmamış doktora tezi. 2003, Ankara.
- [12] M. Keleş, O. Özbek, "Gençlik ve Spor Genel Müdürlüğü Personelinin Örgütsel Sosyalleşme Düzeyleri", Sporometre Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, 6(3), 113-123. 2008.
- [13] G. Kılıçoğlu, D.A. Yılmaz, "Predictive Analysis of Primary School Teachers' Organizational Socialization", Elementary Education Online, 12(4), 1041-1055, 2013.
- [14] E. V. Morrison, "Longitudinal study of the effects of information seeking on newcomer socialization", Journal of Applied Psychology, 78(2), 178-183, 1993.
- [15] C. Ostroff, S.W. Kozlowski, "Organizational socialization as a learning process: The role of information acquisition", Personnel Psychology, 45(4), 849-874, 1992.
- [16] A.M. Saks, and B.E. Ashforth, "Organizational Socialization: Making Sense of the Past and Present as a Prologue for the Future", Journal of Vocational Behavior,; 51(2), 234-279, 1997.
- [17] S.B. Rafanavičienė, T. Sarapovas, P. Barsauskas, "Executive Socialization in Small, Medium and Large Organizations", Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics, 22(4), 434-442, 2011.
- [18] R. J. Taormina, "Convergent validation of two measures of organizational socialization", International Journal of Human Resource Management, 15(1), 76-94, 2004.
- [19] A. Terzi, Örgüt Kültürü, Nobel Yayın Dağıtım, Ankara, 2000.
- [20] Thomas-Cooper, D. Helena, N. Anderson, "Organizational Socialization: A Field Study into Socialization Success and Rate" International Journal of Selection and Assessment, 13(2), 116-128, 2005.
- [21] J.A. Haueter, T.H. Macan, J. Winter, "Measurement of newcomer socialization: Construct validation of a multidimensional scale" Journal of Vocational Behavior, 63, 20-39, 2003.
- [22] F. Ataman. "Predictors of organizational socialization of English instructors at preparatory schools" A Thesis Submitted to the Graduate School of Social Sciences of Middle East Technical University, 1-202, 2012.